

Whole-genome sequencing of the plant growth promoting *Bacillus altitudinis* species isolated from different wild plants growing in the arid region of Tunisia

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Abstract

This study reports the complete genome sequences (CGS) of three strains of *Bacillus altitudinis* namely, B1, B18, and B19 isolated from different plant niches in the arid region of Tunisia. The three strains have shown potential in plant growth promotion, and CGS will provide valuable insights into implications of genes required for its endophytic behaviour and plant growth promotion, which facilitates its development and application in sustainable agriculture. Also, CGS will offer a solid basis for the straightforward genotypic comparison of these strains and the search for niche-specific genomic signatures.

1. Introduction

Nowadays, efforts are being made to switch over to low cost microbial-based technology for plant growth promotion and suppression of harmful diseases and enhancement of crop production. Plants provide a wide range of niches for endophytic organisms that can penetrate and colonize the plant tissues and promote plant growth and resilience to biotic and abiotic challenges throughout the plant's life cycle (Santoyo et al. 2016). Recently, the endophytic *Bacillus altitudinis* has been identified as a promising candidate for biocontrol, bioremediation, and plant growth under abiotic stress conditions (Hasan et al., 2022; Khan et al., 2022; Zhao et al. 2022; Song et al., 2023).

Wild plant species survive in different environments and under diverse stress conditions which explains our plant choices for this study. *Nicotiana glauca* R. C. Graham, also known as "tree tobacco", is perennial woody, invasive, and drought-resistant species in semiarid regions worldwide and several research reported the microbial community of *N. glauca* (Gutierrez-Albanchez et al., 2021; Caravaca et al., 2024). *Tetraena alba* (synonym *Zygophyllum album*) is a halophytic shrub known as a wild desert medicinal plant and is overrepresented in Tunisian arid rangelands (Gamoun et al., 2018). There are few reports on microbes isolated from *T. alba* (Baeshen et al., 2020; Youseif et al., 2023).

All tissues of a plant host bacterial communities: at the rhizosphere, endosphere, and phyllosphere environments. All these microenvironments provide specific biotic and abiotic conditions for the residing bacterial communities (Beckers et al., 2017) and bacteria adapt to their respective niches. Niche-specific adaptations cause genomic modifications resulting in a host-adapted genotype and can be seen as discrete genomic signatures, such as G + C content and genome size variations, presence/absence of virulence factors genes, antimicrobial resistance genes, and differential metabolic potential (de Almeida et al., 2021). Advances in sequencing technologies and the development of robust genome mining tools enable researchers to uncover the molecular basis of the strain versatile lifestyle.

To this end the present investigation was aimed to isolate potential PGPB from the endophytic environments of *N. glauca* and *T. alba* grown in the arid region of Tunisia. We report here the isolation and the whole genome sequence data of three strains of *B. altitudinis* isolated from three different niches.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Collection of plant material

For the isolation of endophytic bacteria, the bacteria B1 and B19 were isolated from the leaves and the roots of *T. alba* respectively which was collected from saline soil in the arid region of Tunisia (Bou ghrara, Mednine, 33°49'70.0"N, 10°63'79.6"E). The bacterium B18 was isolated from the roots of *N. glauca* which was collected from the arid region of Tunisia (Mareth, Gabès, 33°62'57.8"N, 10°28'38.6"E). Samples were placed in clean plastic bags, brought to the laboratory, and used for further experimental purposes.

2.2. Isolation and purification of bacterial endophytes

Leaves and roots were surface-sterilized by a stepwise washing procedure through the following protocol: 70% alcohol for 1 min, sodium hypochlorite (2,5% Cl) for 4 min, ethanol for 30 s, and 3 rinses in sterile distilled water, according to Costa et al. (2012). Afterwards, surface-sterilised leaves and roots were macerated in buffer solution (0,9% NaCl) using a sterile mortar and pestle. Serial tenfold dilutions of the tissue extract were prepared in sterilized distilled water. From each dilution, 100 µl were spread on 10% tryptic soy agar (TSA) plates and incubated at 28 °C. Emerging bacterial colonies were purified through repetitive single-colony isolation.

2.3. Whole-genome sequencing of bacteria

The DNA extraction, the Illumina genome sequencing, and assembly were conducted by the sequencing service provider microbesNG (The BioHub Birmingham, UK) according to their protocols accessible at <https://microbesng.com/>. Briefly, genomic DNA was subjected to whole-genome sequencing on an Illumina NovaSeq 6000 (Illumina, San Diego, USA) using a 250 bp paired end protocol. Reads were trimmed using Trimmomatic version 0.3 and then were de novo assembled into contigs using SPAdes version 3.7. The complete genome sequences were annotated using Prokka version 1.11. The preliminary taxonomic classification of the genome sequence was performed using Kraken. Prediction of protein coding features and tRNA was performed utilizing Prodigal version 2.6, while rRNA prediction was carried out using ARAGORN version 1.2.

2.4. Genome-based taxonomic classification

To confirm the taxonomic assignment generated from Kraken, the Type (Strain) Genome Server (TYGS) was employed (Meier-Kolthoff & Göker, 2019) and the genomes of the resultant type strains were used to calculate the values of average nucleotide sequence identity (ANI) and digital DNA–DNA hybridization (dDDH) between the genomes of B1, B18, and B19 strains and their closely related strains. ANI was calculated using the OrthoANu tool in the EzBioCloud server (Yoon et al., 2017) (<https://www.ezbiocloud.net/tools/ani>), and digital DNA–DNA hybridization (dDDH) values were calculated using the Genome-to-Genome Distance Calculator website service from the DSMZ (GGDC 3.0; <https://ggdc.dsmz.de/ggdc.php#>) and by using formula 2.

Further investigation was done by using the core genes 16S, *rpoB*, *pycA*, and *aroE* for the identification of the B1, B18, and B19 strains. The sequences of the core genes were extracted from the assembled genomes by using the Standalone BLAST program. These sequences were further aligned and compared with the sequences of *Bacillus* species by using the NCBI Basic Local Alignment Search Tools, nucleotide (BLASTn) program available at NCBI (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov>). Alignments of the sequences with the highest homologous hits mined from BLASTn and the gene sequences extracted from the assembled genome were performed using the MUSCLE program in MEGA version 11. Afterwards, a phylogenetic tree was constructed using the maximum likelihood method with 100 bootstrap replicates in MEGA. The phylogenetic tree was visualized with iTOL version 6.

3. Results

3.1. Genomic features

Genomic features of *B. altitudinis* strains B1, B18, and B19 presented similar GC content (41, 2%), N50, and number of sequences of transfer RNA, ribosomal RNA, and transfer-messenger RNA (Table 1).

A slight difference between the strains was observed in terms of genome size, number of coding sequences and number of contigs (Table 1). The genomes of *B. altitudinis* B1, B18, and B19 were assembled into 44, 45, and 36

contigs respectively. The longest genome size was recorded in the strain B1 with a total length of 3,693,926 bp, followed by B19 (3,691,887 bp) and B18 (3,693,039 bp).

Differently, the highest predicted number of CDS was recorded in the strain B1 with a total number of 3890, followed by B18 (3,883), and B19 (3,736).

Table 1. Summary statistics for the genomes *Bacillus altitudinis* strains

	B1	B18	B19
Biosample	leaves of <i>T. alba</i> SAMN37911287	Roots of <i>N. glauca</i> SAMN37252655	Roots of <i>T. alba</i> SAMN38029050
Contigs (>= 1000 bp)	26	27	25
Largest contig	900,597	900,597	900,597
Total length	3,693,926	3,693,039	3,691,887
Mean coverage	57 x	81 x	128 x
GC (%)	41,2	41,2	41,2
N50	356,649	356,649	356,649
CDS	3890	3,883	3,736
tRNA	74	74	74
rRNA	9	9	9
tmRNA	1	1	1
Gene bank accession (assembly)	JAZBQY000000000	JAZBQV000000000	JAZBQX000000000
Gene bank accession (reads)	SRR26533095	SRR25908979	SRR26617761

3.2. Taxonomic classification with average nucleotide identity, digital DNA–DNA hybridization, and phylogenetic analysis

The highest ANI and dDDH values were recorded between the three strains B1, B18, and B19 and the type strain DSM26896 of *B. altitudinis*. These values were lower for the other closely related species (Table 2) especially for *B. xiamenensis* and *B. pumilus* resulting in dDDH values far below 70%; the threshold value for dDDH among different species of bacteria (Chun et al., 2018).

Table 2. dDDH and ANI values between *Bacillus altitudinis* strains and the type strains of the closest relative species

	Strain B1		Strain B18		Strain B19	
	ANI (%)	dDDH (%)	ANI (%)	dDDH (%)	ANI (%)	dDDH (%)
<i>B. altitudinis</i> _DSM26896	98.67	88.20	98.70	88.20	98.69	88.20
<i>B. altitudinis</i> _41KF2b	98.18	83.50	98.17	83.50	98.16	83.50
<i>B. xiamenensis</i> _HYC-10	91.52	44.10	91.65	44.10	91.64	44.10
<i>B. pumilus</i> _NCTC10337	88.96	36.50	88.98	36.50	89.02	36.50

Average Nucleotide Identity (ANI); Digital DNA–DNA hybridization (dDDH)

Based on the phylogenetic analyses, the strains B1, B18, and B19 branched with different *Bacillus* species for the 16S, rpoB, pycA (data not shown) which make them inaccurate core genes for the identification of *B. altitudinis* species. However, the phylogenetic trees constructed from the aroE gene (Figure 1) showed that aroE gene was able to vividly distinguish between *B. altitudinis* and the other closely related species which displayed high specificity for *B. altitudinis*.

Fig 1. Phylogenetic trees of *Bacillus altitudinis* strains. (A) strain B1; (B) strain B18; (C) strain B19. The phylogenetic trees are based on *aroE* gene alignments obtained by MEGA 11 software using the maximum likelihood method. The phylogenetic trees are generated through iTOL.

Data availability

This whole-genome shotgun has been deposited at DDBJ/ENA/GenBank under the accession number JAZBQY000000000, JAZBQV000000000, and JAZBQX000000000. Raw sequence reads have been deposited in the NCBI Sequence Read Archive under the BioProject number PRJNA1011052 and run numbers SRR26533095, SRR25908979, and SRR26617761.

Statement on continuing work

The datasets are being shared prior to formal publication and should be regarded as preliminary.

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